

The study of microplastic imaging in the anatomy of zooplankton based on fluorescent staining

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Abstract. Because of its geographical location and rapid economic development in the district, Shenzhen Bay contains a great number of deposits and pollution. One of the pollutants in Shenzhen Bay is microplastic particles. In such an environment, the accumulation of microplastic particles in zooplankton is critical to the health of the human community due to the process of bioaccumulation. Traditionally, microplastic particles are measured in plankton by removing all organic matter. This experiment aims to use an alternative method of fluorescent imaging to reveal the existence and distribution of microplastics within zooplankton from Shenzhen Bay. Triton X-100 was added without the process of sample fixation by paraformaldehyde to remove lipids and keep potential MPs and other anatomy of the sample. The result proves the method to be capable of removing the lipid within the sample, enhancing the visual effect of microplastics within zooplankton. However, the method also has downsides such as limitations in the size of the sample and possibilities of damaging the sample.

1. Introduction

Shenzhen Bay, due to its unique geographic location, is capable of accumulating deposits from the upper stream river discharge. Sediments that come from soil erosion in the upper reaches of rivers are continuously transported to the middle and lower reaches of rivers. As rivers reach the ocean, it becomes wider, and the flow velocity slows down; sediments accumulate gradually and finally form the estuary area. At the west of Shenzhen city and the boundary between Shenzhen and Hongkong, Shenzhen Bay receives most materials coming from the Pearl River, Dasha River, and some other streams and rivers. Meanwhile, few of these sediments left the bay and most end up trapped in Shenzhen Bay. This feature had contributed to the local ecosystem of Shenzhen Bay such as providing suitable habitat for mangrove forests.

However, this also means that while Shenzhen Bay is capable of catching sediments, it is also capable of catching a great number of pollutants coming from Shenzhen city as well as all facilities from the river upper streams. Research had shown that the water quality in Shenzhen Bay is significantly worse than the outside. This is a mixed result of pollutants from 6 estuaries, a sewage outlet, 34 rainwater outlets, and Shenzhen Bay outlet [1].

Among the many pollutants in Shenzhen Bay include what are known as microplastic particles, which are fragments of plastic less than five millimeters in diameter according to the general definition [2]. Within this range, however, some microplastic particles can be less than 500 micrometers in diameter or less, and the defining size of microplastics varies greatly. Microplastic particles (MPs) were observed in nearly all geographic locations and every biome and ecosystem.

The accumulation of MPs in the body was well known to have the potential to cause serious issues to humans as well as most wildlife. According to the National Institutes of Health, experiments on human cells and mice showed that microplastic buildup in the body can result in inflammation, oxidative stress, disturbed lipid metabolism, gut microbiota dysbiosis, and neurotoxicity [3]. Such buildup in the human body was primarily caused by the ingestion of microplastic from foods. A phenomenon known as bioaccumulation contributed to the buildup. In this process, a trophic level receives in scale, more MPs from its previous trophic levels, since according to the 10% rule, higher trophic levels require more biomass of the trophic levels below to maintain necessary energy consumption.

Due to the high level of MPs in the water of Shenzhen Bay, microplastics likely exist in one of the very basic trophic levels, the zooplankton. Zooplankton are tiny animals that drift or weakly swim along with currents. They feed on phytoplankton, marine snow, other zooplankton, and smaller microorganisms such as protists. Identifying the existence of MPs in zooplankton means that the bioaccumulation of MPs begins at the start and may go through the entire ecosystem of Shenzhen Bay. The consequence was that the organisms of fishery and higher in trophic levels will contain a great number of MPs, then consumed into human body.

Traditional ways to identify microplastics in plankton involve the breakdown of organic matter of plankton to

extract the MPs within [4]. Although such methods allow measurement of the microplastic amount in each unit of biomass, they include certain limits. Such methods are not capable of identifying microplastics within specific species of plankton and are not capable of showing the distribution of MPs in the structure of plankton. To identify these features, the method requires the preservation of major tissue, organs, and body structure of plankton while making MPs within visible.

This experiment aims to develop a method based on fluorescent imaging using samples with fluorescent staining of DAPI, iFlour™ 488 Phalloidin, and Nile Red. From the three fluorescent pigments, Nile Red can bind to lipid molecules and thus emit red signals representing fat tissue. However, Nile Red is also capable to bind with MPs and emitting signal in fluorescent imaging.

In the experiment, 2 experimental sample groups, 1 negative control group, and 1 positive control group were set. One experimental sample group receive standard treatment of fluorescent imaging (details in Method - Experimental samples (Stained with lipid and microplastic)), while another experimental sample group receive fluorescent treatment that was hypothesized to remove lipid in samples (details in Method - Experimental samples (Stained with lipid and microplastic)). The negative control group uses pure samples of MPs without treatment. The Positive control group use pure samples of MPs stained with Nile Red and Phalloidin.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Sampling of zooplankton

The first batch of plankton samples was collected at the estuary of Dasha river 2023/6/26, where the exact GPS was 22°31'14.0"N 113°57'19.1"E. The site includes 2 spots around 10 meters before and after the sluice (Figure 1(sampling site)). At both sites, samples were collected using a plankton net with the ability to sieve out plankton. At both sites, the net was tossed to the surface and dragged back 3 times. In addition, there was another sample collected from the bed of the river. The second batch of plankton samples was collected at the same location where the first batch of plankton samples were collected 2023/6/28 at night. Samples were collected with a light trap on a plankton net and deposited on the surface of the water for 10 minutes. The amphipod samples were collected on the shore of Shenzhen coast near Dasha river 2023/6/26, and the GPS coordinate was 22°31'21.2"N 113°57'10.9"E. Samples were collected by hand. At each abovementioned sampling site, the pH and salinity were measured.

Figure 1: Images of sample of MPs in negative control group.

2.2 Negative control (samples of microplastic without staining)

Pure (Polyethylene terephthalate) PET particles (purchased from HY Plastics Co., Ltd., an agent of raw plastics in Dongguan, China) that have a diameter of around 30 micrometers were observed under the fluorescent microscope with the fluorescent setting for Nile Red stain (see below for more detail on fluorescent microscope setting).

2.3 Positive control (samples of microplastic with fluorescent staining)

The PET particles were stained with Nile Red and observed under the fluorescent microscope with the same fluorescent setting for Nile Red stain (see below for more detail on fluorescent microscope setting).

2.4 Experimental samples for staining lipid and microplastics

Samples were transported to the lab the same day they were collected, where they experienced the process of relaxation and then fixation. During the process of relaxation, the concentrated sample was soaked in 7% MgCl₂ (dissolved in sea water) and stirred for 10 minutes in a centrifuge. After the relaxation, MgCl₂ was removed, and samples were submerged in 4% PFA (paraformaldehyde dissolved in 1x PBS). During this process of fixation,

samples were left in 4-degree Celsius fridge overnight.

On the next day, samples were washed with fresh 1x PBS (137 mM NaCl, 2.7 mM KCl, 10 mM Na₂HPO₄, and 1.8 mM KH₂PO₄) for three times, each wash lasted for 10 minutes. After the washing samples experience penetration, which the samples were emerged in 1x PBS mixed with 0.1% Triton X-100. This process last for at least 3 hours.

After the process penetration, samples were again washed with fresh 1x PBS for 3 times. After that each sample was transferred to a 2 ml centrifuge and added each with 200 mL of PBS containing 0.1% of DAPI (100%), 200 mL of PBS and 0.1% of Nile Red (1mg/ml) and 200 mL of PBS containing 0.1% of iFlour™ 488 Phalloidin (1mg/ml). The sample was then put in 4-degree Celsius fridge away from light for more than 2 hours.

2.5 Experimental samples for staining only microplastics

The processing of samples excluded the step of fixation. The sample was first submerged in 7% MgCl₂, then the sample was directly washed with 1x PBS for three times. After the washing is the penetration process same as mentioned before. After the penetration the samples was washed with 1X PBS, and the sample was then received the fluorescent staining solution same as mentioned before.

2.6 Observation under fluorescent microscope

When the samples are observed, they are washed by 1x PBS for three times and then put under the fluorescent microscope. The samples were exposed to the emission wavelength of each pigment. The emission wavelength of DAPI was 461 nm. The emission wavelength of Nile Red was 635 nm. The emission wavelength of Phalloidin was 488 nm. Prior to observation of experimental samples, the negative control sample, which is the sample without application of fluorescent stain was first observed. Fluorescent intensive, field exposure, and color enhancement setting were set to the point that no fluorescent signal could be detected in the image. These parameters were all recorded and applied in all the subsequent observation of experimental samples, in order to avoid picking up auto-fluorescent signal from the sample.

3. Result

In total, the fluorescent images obtained from the two experimental controls include species of copepod, rotifer, amphipod, and water flea. Samples of copepod belong to three orders, Calanoida, Harpacticoida, and Cyclopoida. Samples of rotifers were species of the family Brachionidae. Samples of amphipods were species of the genus *Niphargus*. Samples of water fleas were species of the genus *Daphnia*. The larvae of copepod and water fleas were identified, however, unable to be classified into families or further.

3.1 Positive and negative control of PET microplastic staining

For the negative control, samples of microplastic without staining were observed under fluorescent microscope. Under the emission wavelength for Nile Red, no signals were observed from the sample of MPs (Figure 1). For the positive control, Under the emission wavelength of Nile Red, samples of microplastic with fluorescent staining were observed with significant signals (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Image of MPs in the positive control group. A is the sample under white light with 4 times magnification. B is the sample under emission wavelength of Nile Red with 4 times magnification. C is the sample under white light with 10 times magnification. D is the sample under emission wavelength of Nile Red with 10 times magnification.

3.2 Characteristic staining patterns of MPs

When analyzing the experimental sample, possible existence of MPs in samples was identified with the following characteristics:

- Shape of dots/speckles with uniformed/overexposed Nile Red signal;
- Brighter Nile Red signal compared to background signal;
- Distinct margin of dots/speckle.

A picture of possible MPs in sample with id “5_ROT_230626_DS_FS_10X” was used as a reference to identify potential MPs (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Image of possible MPs in sample “5_ROT_230626_DS_FS_10X”. Used as reference to identify potential existence of MPs within other samples.

3.3 Experimental samples staining for lipid and microplastic

In total, fluorescent images of 21 samples were obtained in this control group. These samples include three Harpacticoida species, 4 Cyclopoida species, 2 Calanoida species 3 *Daphnia* sp., 4 copepod larvae (unclassified), 1 larva of *Daphnia* sp., 3 Brachionidae sp., and 1 *Niphargus* sp. The results of each sample are concluded in Table 1. For each classification, the detailed result was drawn from one of the samples that belong to the classification.

Table 1. Information of every sample that was imaged in Experimental control group (Stained with lipid and microplastic)

	Sample ID	Sampling site & Date	Sample classification	DAPI signal	Phalloidin signal	(Nile Red signal &) Potential MPs Distribution
1	1_COP_FA-CYC_230626_DS_S	Dasha River After the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Copepod, Family <i>Cyclopoida</i>	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, No Visible MPs
2	2_DAP_230626_DS_FS	Dasha River Before the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Water flea, Genus <i>Daphnia</i>	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, No Visible MPs
3	3_COP_LAR_230626_DS_FS	Dasha River Before the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Copepod Larvae	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, No Visible MPs
4	4_ROT_230626_DS_FS	Dasha River Before the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Rotifer, Family <i>Brachionidae</i>	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, Contain Visible MPs
5	5_ROT_230626_DS_FS	Dasha River Before the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Rotifer, Family <i>Brachionidae</i>	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, Contain Visible MPs
6	6_COP_FA-CYC230626_DS_FS	Dasha River Before the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Copepod, Family <i>Cyclopoida</i>	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, No Visible MPs
7	7_AMP_230626_DS_S	Dasha River Before the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Amphipod, Genus <i>Niphargus</i>	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, No Visible MPs
8	8_COP_FA-CAL_230626_DS_S	Dasha River After the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Copepod, Family <i>Calanoida</i>	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, No Visible MPs
9	9_COP_FA-HAR_230626_DS_S	Dasha River After the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Copepod, Family <i>Harpacticoida</i>	Detected	Detected	Nile Red signal Not detected
10	10_COP_FA-CYC_230626_DS_S	Dasha River After the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Copepod, Family <i>Cyclopoida</i>	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, Contain Visible MPs
11	11_COP_LAR_230626_DS_S	Dasha River After the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Copepod Larvae	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, No Visible MPs
12	12_COP_FA-CYC_230626_DS_S	Dasha River After the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Copepod, Family <i>Cyclopoida</i>	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, No Visible MPs
13	13_ROT_230626_DS_S	Dasha River After the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Rotifer, Family <i>Brachionidae</i>	Not detected	Not detected	Nile Red Signal detected, No Visible MPs
14	14_COP_LAR_230626_DS_S	Dasha River After the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Copepod Larvae	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, No Visible MPs
15	15_COP_LAR_230626_DS_S	Dasha River After the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Copepod Larvae	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, Contain Visible MPs
16	16_DAP_230626_DS_S	Dasha River After the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Water Flea, Genus <i>Daphnia</i>	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, No Visible MPs
17	17_DAP_230626_DS_S	Dasha River After the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Water Flea, Genus <i>Daphnia</i>	Not detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, No Visible MPs
18	18_DAP_LAR_230626_DS_S	Dasha River After the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Water Flea Larvae, Genus <i>Daphnia</i>	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, No Visible MPs
19	19_COP_FA-CYC_230626_DS_S	Dasha River After the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Copepod, Family <i>Harpacticoida</i>	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, No Visible MPs
20	20_COP_FA-CAL_230626_DS_S	Dasha River After the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Copepod, Family <i>Calanoida</i>	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, Contain Visible MPs
21	21_COP_FA-Cyc_230626_DS_S	Dasha River After the Sluice, 2023.06.26	Copepod, Family <i>Cyclopoida</i>	Detected	Detected	Nile Red Signal detected, No Visible MPs

In the set of images labeled “20_COP_FA-CAL_230626_DS_S” was a sample of a *Calanoida* sp. collected from Dasha River after the sluice. Under the emission wavelength of DAPI, images demonstrated significant, grainy signals all over the body, appendages, tail, and antenna. Stronger signals are also concentrated near the center of the body, close to the base of appendages. Under the emission wavelength of Nile Red, images showed significant and evenly distributed signals mainly in the body, and weak signals in the antenna and tail. One particular strong signal located in the body (pointed out in the figure) was noticed. Under the emission wavelength of Phalloidin, images show stripped and segmented signals in the body, appendages, and antenna (Figure 4).

Figure 4: The microscopic Image of sample 20_COP_FA-CAL_230626_DS_S with magnification of 4 times. A is the sample under white light; B is the sample under DAPI emission wavelength. C is the sample under Nile Red emission wavelength. D is the sample under Phalloidin emission wavelength. Notice that potential existence of MPs signal was pointed out with the white arrow in C.

Figure 5: The microscopic Image of sample 21_COP_FA-CYC_230626_DS_S with magnification of 10 times. A is the sample under white light; B is the sample under DAPI emission wavelength. C is the sample under Nile Red emission wavelength. D is the sample under Phalloidin emission wavelength.

In the set of images labeled “21_COP_FA-Cyc_230626_DS_S” was a sample of Cyclopoida species collected from the Dasha River after the sluice. Under the emission wavelength of DAPI, images demonstrated significant, grainy signals could be observed all over the body, tail, and antenna. Stronger signals are also detected at the center of the body. Under the emission wavelength of Nile Red, red fluorescent signals are significant and evenly distributed mainly in the body, and weak signals could be observed in the tail. No particular strong signals were identified from the evenly distributed signals. Under the emission wavelength of Phalloidin, images showed stripped and segmented signals in the body, tail, and antenna (Figure 5).

In the set of images labeled “19_COP_FA-HAR_230626_DS_S” was a sample of Harpacticoida species collected from the Dasha River after the sluice. Under the emission wavelength of DAPI, images demonstrated significant, grainy signals all over the body, tails, and antenna. Stronger signals were observed as well near the front of the body and antenna. Under the emission wavelength of Nile Red, images showed significant and evenly distributed signals mainly in the body, and weak signals in the tail. However, nine strong spotted signals were identified located in the body of the sample. Under the emission wavelength of Phalloidin, images showed stripped and segmented signals in the body, tail, and antenna like those mentioned above (Figure 6).

Figure 6: The microscopic Image of sample 19_COP_FA-HAR_230626_DS_S with magnification of 10 times. A is the sample under white light; **B** is the sample under DAPI emission wavelength. **C** is the sample under Nile Red emission wavelength. **D** is the sample under Phalloidin emission wavelength. Notice that the potential existence of MPs signal was pointed out with the white arrow and white box in **C**.

In the set of images labeled “17_FA_DAP_230626_DS_FS” was a sample of *Daphnia* sp. collected from the Dasha River before the sluice. Under the emission wavelength of Nile Red, images showed evenly distributed weak signals located in the appendages, digestive system, and the two larvae the sample carried. No strong Nile Red signals were observed among the body. Under the emission wavelength of Phalloidin, images show strong signals located in the digestive system (Figure 7).

In the set of images labeled “5_ROT_230626_DS_S” was a sample of Brachionidae species collected from the Dasha River after the sluice. Under the emission wavelength of DAPI, the sample showed grainy signals located near the mouthpart and body. Under the emission wavelength of Nile Red, strong and even signals were observed in the two egg sacs the sample carried. Besides this, particularly strong spotted signals were concentrated near the mouthpart of the sample. Under the emission wavelength of Phalloidin, the sample shows strong, spotted, and stripped signals symmetrically distributed in the body and concentrated in the mouthpart of the sample (Figure 8).

In the set of images labeled “7_AMP_230626_DS_S” was a sample of *Niphargus* sp. collected from the Dasha River after the sluice. Under the emission wavelength of DAPI, the sample showed strong background signals from the exoskeleton, and some grainy signals located throughout the anatomy. Under the emission wavelength of Nile Red, signals are unrecognizable due to strong background signals. Under the emission wavelength of Phalloidin, the sample shows significant signals located in the appendages and digestive system of samples (Figure 9).

Figure 7: The microscopic Image of sample 17_DAP_230626_DS_S with magnification of 10 times. A is the sample under white light; B is the sample under DAPI emission wavelength. C is the sample under Nile Red emission wavelength. D is the sample under Phalloidin emission wavelength.

Figure 8: The microscopic Image of sample 5_ROT_230626_DS_FS with magnification of 10 times. A is the sample under white light; B is the sample under DAPI emission wavelength. C is the sample under Nile Red emission wavelength. D is the sample under Phalloidin emission wavelength. Notice that the potential existence of MPs signal was pointed out with the white arrow and white box in C.

Figure 9: The microscopic Image of sample 7_AMP_230626_DS_S with magnification of 10 times. **A** is the sample under white light; **B** is the sample under DAPI emission wavelength. **C** is the sample under Nile Red emission wavelength. **D** is the sample under Phalloidin emission wavelength.

In the set of images labeled “15_COP_LAR_230626_DS_S” was a sample of Copepod Larvae collected from the Dasha River after the sluice. Under the emission wavelength of DAPI, the sample showed grainy signals located throughout the body. Under the emission wavelength of Nile Red, an even signal was observed throughout the body. Two particular strong signals were also noticed, as pointed out in the figure. Significant, stripped, and segmented signals were observed located in the central body and appendages (Figure 10).

Figure 10: The microscopic Image of sample 15_COP_LAR_230626_DS_S with magnification of 10 times. **A** is the sample under white light; **B** is the sample under DAPI emission wavelength. **C** is the sample under Nile Red emission wavelength. **D** is the sample under Phalloidin emission wavelength. Notice that the potential existence of MPs signal was pointed out with the white arrow and white box in C.

3.4 Experimental samples (stained with only microplastic)

Images of samples that were obtained in the group of samples with the lipid in them removed include Harpacticoida

sp., *Calanoida* sp. and *Niphargus* sp.

In all samples of *Harpacticoida* sp. and *Calanoida* sp. imaged, little to no Nile Red background signals were detected, and strong, spot-like signals were observed in significant amount that concentrates and the central body and digestive system. Under white light, most samples demonstrate complete anatomy, structure of muscle, and tissues were visible and similar to the experimental samples (Stained with lipid and microplastic) (Figure 11). However, some samples' anatomy was observed to be damaged. As an example, the only *Calanoida* sp. sample imaged demonstrated Nile Red signals similar to other samples but lacked tail structure. Another sample of *Calanoida* sp. seems to have no internal structure and only the exoskeleton remained (Figure 12).

The sample of *Niphargus* sp. showed suspected MPs signal in its digestive system. However, the result is uncertain due to the strong background signals of sample (Figure 13).

Figure 11: Images of 2 samples of *Harpacticoida* sp. On the left was the white light image of sample under 10 times magnification. On the right was the Nile Red signal of sample under 10 times magnification.

Figure 12: Images of samples that are damaged in the Experimental control (stained with only microplastic)

Figure 13: Images of sample of *Niphargus* sp. in the Experimental control (stained with only microplastic).

4. Discussion

The result of negative and positive control proved that in the experiment, the sample of microplastic particles has no self-emitting fluorescence that matches Nile Red signals. It was also confirmed that MPs can show significant signals when stained with Nile Red pigment.

Among the samples of the two experimental controls, MPs were found in samples of Harpacticoida species, Calanoida species, Brachionidae species and Copepod larvae treated with the procedure of Experimental samples (Stained with lipid and microplastic); and all imaged samples in experimental control (stained with only microplastic) except *Niphargus* sp., which includes *Harpacticoida* species, *Calanoida* species, was observed with MPs within. From the data of experimental samples (stained with lipid and microplastic) (Figure 3), *Brachionidae* sp. demonstrated the most distinct possible MPs distribution without the lipid-removing method applied. This shows its anatomy of exoskeleton with a higher opacity and less storage of lipid compared to other samples. Its egg, however, emits even background color due to presence of lipid.

The result of the 2 groups of experimental samples shows that the method that attempts to remove lipids and remain with only the Nile Red signals of MPs is feasible. In the method, the sample was not fixed and when the Triton-x 100 was added, it penetrated the exoskeleton and cell membrane, eventually dissolved the lipids in the sample. Compared to the samples that were not treated with the method, samples that were treated with the method had little to no Nile Red signals other than signals coming from MPs. Some images of certain species such as the rotifer were observed to have significant signals of MPs even without the special treatment that removes the lipid. The distribution of MPs within samples also follows certain trends; MPs are usually found in the digestive system or near the mouthpart of samples. Overall, the method still increases the accuracy of identifying MP distribution within samples compared to regular fluorescent staining process.

This method provides an alternative, novel, and practical way to demonstrate the existence of MPs within plankton in a broad and visual perspective. It also reveals the presence of a type of crucial marine pollutant in the very early trophic level of Shenzhen's marine ecosystem. This method can also be applied to more species of plankton in Shenzhen Coast and by doing so, the potential differences in the amount and localization of MPs within different types of plankton can be revealed. In such cases, a small scale of bioaccumulation can be observed that may aid the calculation of the accumulation of MPs in organisms that are in higher trophic levels.

On the other hand, this method also includes some limitations. Since the anatomy structure of samples remains, the exact number of MPs was not able to be measured based on this method. Another limitation is that it is hard to apply to zooplanktons with a size larger than 500 micrometers, and zooplanktons that have thick exoskeleton. In such situations, the background signal of Nile Red fluorescent signal may interfere with the signal of MPs. Besides this, the method can also lead to damage to the structure of a proportion of the sample.

5. Conclusion

Overall, the experiment demonstrated that while method of removing lipid in the process of staining are absent, all samples except for samples of *Brachionidae* sp. emit strong background signal of Nile Red which interferes with the potentially MPs signals; When the method was applied, all samples observed demonstrated significant MPs signal without background signals. The method proves to be efficient of removing background signals of samples with relatively thinner exoskeleton but are inefficient against samples such as *Niphargus* sp. with relatively thicker exoskeleton and have a possibility of breaking the anatomy of sample.

The result suggests that in Shenzhen Bay, MPs exist within the very base of the food chain. This suggest that organisms higher in the trophic levels within the ecosystem of Shenzhen Bay, including those considered as part of fishery and having economic values, likely contain an accumulated number of MPs within, proposing threats on health status to those who consumes the organisms.

References:

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